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Research Article

**PREDICTIVE VALUE OF TACHYPNEA IN THE DIAGNOSIS
OF BRONCHOPNEUMONIA IN THE PEDIATRIC
POPULATION**Sumayyah Ahmed Nezar Kobeisy², Saleh Al Harbi^{1,2}¹Department of Paediatrics, Umm Al-Qura University, Mecca²Department of Pediatric, Dr. Soliman Fakeeh Hospital, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia

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Abstract:

Background: Pneumonia is the leading cause of morbidity and mortality in children less than 5 years of age (Rudan, *et al.* 2008). Studies on the values of tachypnea in the diagnosis of pneumonia in children are limited (Shah, Bachur, Kim & Neuman 2010).

Objective: To identify the clinical predictive values of age related tachypnea in children with radiographic evidence of bronchopneumonia.

Methods: A retrospective cohort study was conducted at Dr. Soliman Fakeeh Hospital. The aim of the study was to seek an association between respiratory rate and radiographic pneumonia in the pediatric age group. Data was collected and analyzed in IBM SPSS Version 20.

Results: It was found that there was statistical significance in the likelihood ratio of a relationship between respiratory rate and radiographic pneumonia in the infant age group [$G^2(1, N = 215) = 4.252, p = .039$]. The results were also significant for tachypnea in the toddler age group [$\chi^2(1, N = 334) = 6.501, p = .011$]. Approximately 94% of tachypneic toddlers had pneumonia.

Conclusion: Due to the high level of specificity and positive predictive value, evaluation of respiratory rate for age related tachypnea may be useful in the assessment of pneumonia risk among children in settings with underprivileged resources.

Key Words: Tachypnea, bronchopneumonia, predictive value, pediatrics

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INTRODUCTION:

Pneumonia is the leading cause of morbidity and mortality in children less than 5 years of age (Rudan, et al. 2008). Despite the high incidence of childhood pneumonia worldwide, data is limited regarding the ability to diagnose and predict the clinical course of pneumonia (Florin, French, Zorc, Alpern, & Shah 2013). Studies on the value of tachypnea in the diagnosis of pneumonia in children are limited (Shah, Bachur, Kim & Neuman 2010). As of 2015, it has been estimated that approximately 120-156 million cases of acute lower respiratory tract infections occur worldwide and result in 1.4 million deaths with more than 95% of the morbidities in lower and middle income countries (Lazzerini, Sonogo, & Pellegrin 2015). In a recent study, it was found that children under the age of five years suffering from severe pneumonia associated with hypoxia had a higher chance of having age related tachypnea (Alwadhi, Dewan, Malhorta, Shah, & Gupta 2017).

We therefore found it appropriate to conduct this study to identify the clinical predictive values of age related tachypnea in children with radiographic evidence of bronchopneumonia.

METHODS:**Study Design:**

A retrospective cohort study was conducted at Dr. Soliman Fakeeh Hospital in the port city of Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. The aim of the study was to seek an association between respiratory rate and radiographic pneumonia in the pediatric age group.

Participants and Enrollment:

Data was extracted retrospectively from, OASIS, the hospital electronic medical record operating system, between the dates of January 1, 2014 to December 18, 2018. Inclusion criteria were any pediatric patient that presented to the hospital with documented respiratory rate and pulse oxygen saturation and with physician diagnosed bronchopneumonia. Patients were excluded from the study if a chest x-ray was not done to show evidence of bronchopneumonia.

Outcomes and Definitions:

Patients were stratified into five categories based on age related respiratory rates as determined by the 2018 PALS study guide for age related respiratory rates (RR) (Aehlert 2018). The age categories were: less than one year of age (infant), one to three years (toddler), four to five years (preschooler), six to 12 years (school aged child), and 13 to 18 years of age (adolescent).

Tachypnea was defined as a respiratory rate (RR) greater than 61 breaths per minute in the first age group, > 41 in the second group, > 35 in the third, > 31 in the fourth and > 17 in the fifth category. Hypoxemia was considered as a pulse oxygen saturation less than 95% across all age groups.

Data Collection and Analysis:

Data was collected and analyzed in IBM SPSS Statistics version 20. Pearson Chi square (χ^2), Chi-square likelihood ratio (G^2) and Fisher's exact appropriate tests were applied to compare the rate of radiological pneumonia among children with and without age-defined. Results were defined in terms of sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV) and negative predictive value (NPV). A probability below 0.05 was regarded as statistically significant. The strength of association between tachypnea and radiological evidence of bronchopneumonia was determined by the Phi correlation coefficient. Each age group RR was analyzed for association with hypoxemia using the Chi-square test.

RESULTS:

A total of 755 patients were enrolled in the study and were diagnosed to have clinical bronchopneumonia based on history and physical examination. The toddler age group constituted approximately 44% of the studied population and infants were around 29%. The adolescent age group did not contribute significantly to the study since only one participant qualified (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Distribution of Participants Based on Age

The study showed that 85% of those enrolled were found to have radiographic evidence of bronchopneumonia.

In the infant age group, all the participants who were tachypneic were also hypoxemic and had evidence of radiographic pneumonia. However only 40.5% of those with pneumonia were hypoxic and tachypneic [$G^2(1, N = 38) = 1.022, p = .312$]. On the other hand, 96.9% of infants without pneumonia had a normal saturation and normal RR and only 7.6% of infants with pneumonia were tachypneic despite normal saturation [$G^2(1, N = 177) = .979, p = .322$].

It was found that there was statistical significance in the likelihood ratio of a relationship between respiratory rate and radiographic pneumonia in the infant age group [$G^2(1, N = 215) = 4.252, p = .039$].

In the toddler category, 91.9% of tachypneic toddlers were hypoxemic and had pneumonia. There was a statistically significant positive association between normal saturation and normal RR with a normal chest x-ray [$G^2(1, N = 273) = 7.233, p = .007$]. There was a positive statistical significance in the relationship between RR and radiographic pneumonia in toddlers [$\chi^2(1, N = 334) = 6.501, p = .011$].

Although most of the tachypneic preschoolers and school age children were hypoxemic and had pneumonia, there was no statistical significance to associate respiratory rate and the presence of pneumonia in either group.

Although the p values were statistically significant, the phi correlation coefficient for tachypnea in the toddler age group was .140. This correlate with a slightly positive association of respiratory rate with radiographic evidence of bronchopneumonia.

The allocation of patients with and without pneumonia with combinations of RR and SPO2 is shown in Table

1. Overall, the results were significant for tachypnea in the infant and toddler age groups.

Table 1: Distribution of signs based on Sensitivity and Specificity

Sign	Sensitivity%	Specificity%	PPV%	NPV%	P- Value
Age Group: Infant					
Infant RR (N= 215)	14.3	97	96.3	17	.039
RR and Hypoxemia (N=38)	40.5	100	100	4.3	.312
RR and Normal SPO2 (N=177)	7.6	96.9	91.7	18.8	.322
Age Group: Toddler					
Toddler RR (N= 334)	26.8	90	93.8	17.8	.011
RR and Hypoxemia (N=61)	59.6	25	91.9	4.2	.532
RR and Normal SPO2 (N=273)	18.5	95.7	95.5	19.2	.007
Age Group: Preschooler					
Preschooler (N= 92)	22.1	86.7	89.5	17.8	.728
RR and Hypoxemia (N=12)	60	50	85.7	20	.795
RR and Normal SPO2 (N=80)	16.4	92.3	91.7	17.6	.387
Age Group: School Age Child					
School Age children (N= 113)	15.2	100	100	14.3	.209
RR and Hypoxemia (N=24)	52.2	100	100	8.3	.232
RR and Normal SPO2 (N=89)	3.9	100	100	15.1	.326

DISCUSSION:

We retrospectively examined the association between tachypnea with radiographic pneumonia among 755 children presenting to our hospital who had a chest x-ray obtained for possible pneumonia. The association of radiographic pneumonia and tachypnea was significant only in the infant and toddler age groups. This is probably due to the fact that the majority of the participants were in these categories.

This study had a high specificity and lack of sensitivity for tachypnea in the infant and toddler age groups similar to the study done by Mullholland, Olinsky, & Shann in 1990 and unlike the study done by Kushwah, Verma, & Gaur in 2018.

The systematic review and meta-analysis conducted by Lazzerini, Marzia, et al. in 2015, supported the regular use of pulse oxygen saturation to aid in recognition children with increased morbidity due to acute lower respiratory tract infections.

The generalizability of our study may be limited because our study was conducted in a region of Saudi Arabia where there is widespread access to healthcare and clinicians are more likely to see patients earlier in the course of their illness and with less advanced pneumonias. In addition, the port city of Jeddah accommodates a massive variety of expatriates not found elsewhere in the country and it is considered as the main entryway to the pilgrims hosted by Saudi Arabia, therefore the sample size in our study may not

be reflective of the population in other areas of the country.

Moreover, we did not exclude children with underlying medical conditions that may affect the respiratory rate such as congenital heart disease and neuromuscular disorders. Although some patients presented with symptoms indicative of pneumonia such as fever or cough, patients that did not undergo chest radiography were not included in the study. Furthermore, respiratory rate was not adjusted for temperature.

Since there is no ideal standard for the definition of pneumonia we included equivocal radiographs to decrease the chance of missing a child with radiographic pneumonia. Due to the minimal enrollment in the adolescent age group, we did not have the statistical power to evaluate the association between tachypnea and radiographic pneumonia among children between 13 to 18 years of age.

CONCLUSION:

In the modern health care setting, tachypnea is not a sensitive indicator of pneumonia and may be aided by the supplementation of pulse oxygen saturation. Due to the high level of specificity and positive predictive value, evaluation of respiratory rate for age related tachypnea may be useful in the assessment of pneumonia risk among children in settings with underprivileged resources. Further studies should focus on more rural areas of Saudi Arabia with fewer

medical resources and should include a larger sample. Medical facilities should strive to have pulse oximetry available in all areas.

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Conflict of Interest: none declared

Ethical Approval:

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